

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 2

Data Management Plan

Deliverable D7.4

The project Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 2 (ESiWACE2) has received funding from the European Union's
Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme
under Grant Agreement No 823988

About this document

Work package in charge: WP7 Scientific Coordination, Management and Dissemination

Actual delivery date for this deliverable: 30 June 2019

Dissemination level: PU (for public use)

Lead author

Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum GmbH (DKRZ): Philipp Neumann

Contact details

Project Office: esiwace@dkrz.de

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Appendix: Data Management Plan, Version 1.0

1. Abstract /publishable summary

The data management plan “describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by”¹ ESIWACE2 in all relevant work packages. It will be updated throughout the project period in time with the periodic project evaluation.

With ESIWACE2 focussing on software development and the preparation of the weather and climate communities for exascale computing in terms of services and infrastructural means, only few actual “research data” are created in the project. They can be basically grouped into three categories: (1) model output for development purposes, (2) performance analysis and benchmark data, and (3) educational material.

2. Conclusion & Results

At the time of writing the first version of the data management plan, it is only the management of few data which is considered essential for the project ESIWACE2 and the weather/climate/HPC communities. This might change over the duration of the project. In accordance with the project’s Description of Action, the data management plan will therefore be revised and submitted to the European Commission as an integral part of the periodic reports.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	Yes
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	Yes

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	Yes
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	Yes
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	Yes
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	Yes
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	Yes
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	Yes

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm#A1-template

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

In the Description of Action of ESIWACE2, the management of research data generated/collected during the project has been explained and broken down onto the different work packages:

WP1: *High-resolution model output will be generated for testing purposes and inter-comparison. Parts thereof are anticipated to be made available and shared publicly (for example in the scope of the project DYAMOND, see WP 1, Task 1.1). Output is based on community standards (NetCDF, grib). Data are provided and preserved through consortium partners (e.g., DKRZ); no cost will apply. Besides, performance data are generated and shared among the consortium.*

WP2: *This WP aims at technology watch and does not generate numerical or other relevant data sets.*

WP3: *This WP provides services and therefore does not generate numerical or other relevant data sets.*

WP4: *This WP is not expected to be collecting data which needs long-term curation. Any data collected will either be performance data of specific codes on specific hardware (and thus have little/no likelihood of re-use), or it will be incorporated into performance models which will be made available in software repositories. If data is collected for longer-term use, NetCDF standards will be used; data will be deposited in CEDA archives (<http://www.ceda.ac.uk>). CEDA is a partner via UKRI; no cost for curation will apply.*

WP5: *This WP will investigate implementations and methods for post-processing, visualisation and data analytics at scale. No numerical or other relevant data sets are expected to be created or collected. Rather, tools and applications that will allow weather and climate data post-processing, analysis and visualisation at scale will be provided. NetCDF will be the standard data format for data sets managed in WP5.*

WP6: *Teaching OER material (task 6.2) will be created and made available under a permissive CC-by licence. No cost will apply.*

WP 7: *This WP takes care of project management and does not create numerical or other relevant data sets.” (Description of Action, Sec. 2.2, a3), pages 25-26)*

In the first months of the project, the consortium has re-visited the topic of data management in the project and collected all relevant data sets in this data management plan, version 1.0. The data can be basically grouped into three categories:

- (1) Model output for development purposes: these are data generated by actual model runs on supercomputer platforms in WP1. The model output will be used to check the developments for correctness, to investigate and improve scalability of I/O, etc. It will most probably not be used directly for scientific studies, since the software development focus implies rather short simulation periods. No long-term archival is therefore anticipated, but only short-term storage, that is keeping the data for a few months. Depending on the current state of development, the overall contents and form of the model output (in terms of variables written to the files) might change over the project period.
- (2) Performance analysis and benchmark data: these are the data referred to for WP1 and WP4. To measure the success of model and code tuning and to enable a comparison

among models, code optimisation steps and model runs on different pieces of hardware, performance data are collected.

Benchmark data have been added for WP3 as they were found to be not only essential for the project consortium for the purpose of performance reproducibility, comparison and maintainability, but also potentially for a wider audience in the future.

- (3) Teaching material: this refers to the material produced in the scope of WP6. ESIWACE2 strives for training on various exascale-relevant topics including IO, domain-specific languages or data analytics, feeding the weather and climate communities' demand. Despite being developed rather specifically for the weather and climate modelling sector, the training material is expected to be supportive for researchers, software developers and (under-)graduates who are interested in HPC-aware large-scale software development at the edge of current computing and IO capability.

After a careful review, it was found that all other WPs do not generate numerical data sets that are relevant for data management.

5. References (*Bibliography*)

- Participant Portal H2020 Online Manual, Data management, http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm#A1-template, 21 March 2019
- Participant Portal H2020 Online Manual, Template for the Data Management Plan, http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/gm/reporting/h2020-tpl-oa-data-mgt-plan_en.docx, 21 March 2019

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

None.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

FAIR data management is an essential building block for reproducibility and reusability of data in research, science and development. In the scope of the European HPC strategy, the performance analysis and benchmark data represent means to actually pave the way towards reproducibility and comparability of performance on current supercomputers as well as on the upcoming pre-exascale and exascale systems, that are aimed at through the European HPC Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC).

The training material will support the education of scientists and model developers to make use of pre-exascale and exascale architectures in the future. This goes hand in hand with profound knowledge on advanced programming techniques (such as domain-specific languages) and IO, as well as on emerging trends that shape future architectures such as data analytics.

8. Sustainability

The data management plan helps at identifying data that is created, collected and/or processed in ESIWACE2 and describes how to make these data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). This contributes to sustaining the provision, access and use of the data.

9. Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is the general public (PU).

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

The deliverable is provided on Zenodo.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

A publication of the High-Performance Weather and Climate benchmarks shall be prepared in the future.

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

None.

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

Does not apply.

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 2

Data Management Plan of ESIWACE2

Version 1.0 of 30 June 2019

The project Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe Phase 2 (ESIWACE2) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 823988

1. Summary

This document describes the data, that are created in the scope of the centre of excellence in simulation of weather and climate in Europe, phase 2 (ESiWACE2), and their FAIR management. With ESIWACE2 focussing on software development and the preparation of the weather and climate communities for exascale computing in terms of services and infrastructural means, only few actual “research data” are created in the project. They can be basically grouped into three categories which are briefly described in the following:

- Model output for development purposes: to check for (scalability behaviour of) I/O during simulations and to check for correctness of the models, model output will be produced. This model output is of marginal scientific value since only short time intervals will typically be considered for testing and evaluation of scalability. Yet, storing the data for a short period of time (that is O(months)) is a valuable step for single-model development.
- Performance analysis and benchmark data: to measure the success of model and code tuning and to enable a comparison among models, code optimisation steps and model runs on different pieces of hardware, performance analysis data are collected. As hardware and underlying software is rapidly progressing, long-term archival of these data is considered to be of limited use. However, for the duration of the project, several performance and run time data are being collected, stored and shared—particularly, but not exclusively—among the project consortium. Performance data from the High-Performance Climate and Weather (HPCW) benchmarks that are to be further developed and promoted through ESIWACE2 will form a basis for current and future hardware and software performance comparison. Yet, it is again the development of the benchmarks which is the focus of ESIWACE2, rather than the actual employment of the benchmarks to compare various performance characteristics. These data will be valuable to model developers to understand current performance limits and bottlenecks on pre-exascale and upcoming exascale systems. Data size will be rather limited.
- Training material: to pave the way towards weather and climate modelling on exascale architectures, education and training for scientists and model developers is of utmost importance. ESIWACE2 strives for training on various exascale-relevant topics including IO, domain-specific languages (DSLs) or data analytics, feeding the weather and climate communities’ demand. Despite being developed rather specifically for the weather and climate modelling sector, the training material is expected to be supportive for researchers, software developers and (under-)graduates who are interested in HPC-aware large-scale software development at the edge of current computing and IO capability. It will be provided via the Open Educational Resources and will be thus findable, re-usable, and openly accessible to everyone.

Data security and ethical concerns do not apply to ESIWACE2 data. Allocation costs are currently not expected.

2. Datasets

Data reference name	EC-Earth model output
Contact	Kim Serradell (kim.serradell@bsc.es), Uwe Fladrich (uwe.fladrich@smhi.se)
Data summary and description	<p>Objectives: Data to validate model fidelity of model runs in production mode at high resolution.</p> <p>Relation to work programme: W1, WP4, WP5. Data output is required for production mode simulations in WP1. Information about data types and volumes are important for WP4 and WP5.</p> <p>Data generation: Data is generated via model simulations with EC-Earth at high resolution.</p> <p>Data format/type: Standard model output in GRIB and NetCDF format.</p> <p>Expected data size: O(Terabytes).</p>
FAIR aspects	<p>Findable: The data volume and types will be reported in deliverable D1.1. The model data may also be evaluated for scientific studies to optimise model fidelity at high resolution.</p> <p>Accessible: The data will be made available, via download from BSC, for research purposes on request directed to the contacts named above.</p> <p>Interoperable: The data is labelled using the standard model nomenclature of the GRIB and NetCDF formats and should be readable and usable by any domain scientist. However, the size of the data will make it difficult for non-experts to handle the data.</p> <p>Re-usable: No long-term archival of the data is anticipated and the exact description of the data (variable fields etc.) may change over the course of the project: the scientific value of model data of the production mode simulations will be very limited since simulations will be short due to the focus on scalability. The scientific evaluation will rather be performed via high-resolution model inter-comparison projects (such as DYAMOND) in contrast to ESIWACE2. However, the data is not licensed and available for research purposes.</p>
Allocation costs	No additional cost.
Data security	The data will be stored on the BSC file systems for a limited time; see also FAIR aspect “Re-usable” above.
Ethical aspects	None.

Data reference name	ICON model output
Contact	Philipp Neumann (neumann@dkrz.de), Reinhard Budich (reinhard.budich@mpimet.mpg.de)
Data summary and description	<p>Objectives: Data to validate model fidelity of model runs in production mode at high resolution.</p> <p>Relation to work programme: W1, WP4, WP5. Data output is required for production mode simulations in WP1. Information about data types and volumes are important for WP4 and WP5.</p> <p>Data generation: Data is generated via model simulations with ICON at high resolution.</p> <p>Data format/type: Standard model output in GRIB and NetCDF format.</p> <p>Expected data size: O(Terabytes).</p>
FAIR aspects	<p>Findable: The data volume and types will be reported in deliverable D1.1. The model data may also be evaluated for scientific studies to optimise model fidelity at high resolution.</p> <p>Accessible: The data will be made available, via download from DKRZ, for research purposes on request directed to the contacts named above.</p> <p>Interoperable: The data is labelled using the standard model nomenclature of the GRIB and NetCDF formats and should be readable and usable by any domain scientist. However, the size of the data will make it difficult for non-experts to handle the data.</p> <p>Re-usable: No long-term archival of the data is anticipated and the exact description of the data (variable fields etc.) may change over the course of the project: the scientific value of model data of the production mode simulations will be very limited since simulations will be short due to the focus on scalability. The scientific evaluation will rather be performed via high-resolution model inter-comparison projects (such as DYAMOND) in contrast to ESIWACE2. However, the data is not licensed and available for research purposes.</p>
Allocation costs	No additional cost.
Data security	The data will be stored on the DKRZ file systems for a limited time; see also FAIR aspect “Re-usable” above.
Ethical aspects	None.

Data reference name	IFS model output
Contact	Peter Dueben (peter.dueben@ecmwf.int)
Data summary and description	<p>Objectives: Data to validate model fidelity of model runs in production mode at high resolution.</p> <p>Relation to work programme: W1, WP4, WP5. Data output is required for production mode simulations in WP1. Information about data types and volumes are important for WP4 and WP5.</p> <p>Data generation: Data is generated via model simulations with the coupled IFS at high resolution. Data can be re-used for (bit-)reproducibility tests for runs on different parallel configurations and supercomputers.</p> <p>Data format/type: Standard model output in GRIB and NetCDF format.</p> <p>Expected data size: O(Terabytes).</p>
FAIR aspects	<p>Findable: The data volume and types will be reported in deliverable D.1.1. The model data may also be evaluated for scientific studies to optimise model fidelity at high resolution.</p> <p>Accessible: The data can be accessed for research purposes via ECMWF’s ftp server. Data can be shared within the consortium. For external requests, data requests need to be sent to peter.dueben@ecmwf.int.</p> <p>Interoperable: The data is labelled using the standard model nomenclature of the GRIB and NetCDF formats and should be readable and usable by any domain scientist. However, the size of the data will make it difficult for non-experts to handle the data.</p> <p>Re-usable: No long-term archival of the data is anticipated and the exact description of the data (variable fields etc.) may change over the course of the project: the scientific value of model data of the production mode simulations will be very limited since simulations will be short due to the focus on scalability. The scientific evaluation will rather be performed via high-resolution model inter-comparison projects (such as DYAMOND) in contrast to ESIWACE2. However, the data is not licensed and available for research purposes.</p>
Allocation costs	No additional cost.
Data security	The data will be stored on the tape archive of ECMWF. Data may get removed as model developments progress, see also FAIR aspect “Re-usable” above.
Ethical aspects	None.

Data reference name	IPSL model output
Contact	Thomas Dubos (dubos@lmd.polytechnique.fr)
Data summary and description	<p>Objectives: Data to validate model fidelity of model runs in production mode at high resolution.</p> <p>Relation to work programme: W1, WP4, WP5. Data output is required for production mode simulations in WP1. Information about data types and volumes are important for WP4 and WP5.</p> <p>Data generation: Data is generated via model simulations with the IPSL model at high resolution.</p> <p>Data format/type: Standard model output in NetCDF format.</p> <p>Expected data size: O(Terabytes).</p>
FAIR aspects	<p>Findable: The data volume and types will be reported in deliverable D.1.1. The model data may also be evaluated for scientific studies to optimise model fidelity at high resolution.</p> <p>Accessible: The data will be made available, via download from IPSL or TGCC computing center, for research purposes on request directed to the contacts named above.</p> <p>Interoperable: The data is labelled using the standard model nomenclature of the NetCDF format and should be readable and usable by any domain scientist. However, the size of the data will make it difficult for non-experts to handle the data.</p> <p>Re-usable: No long-term archival of the data is anticipated and the exact description of the data (variable fields etc.) may change over the course of the project: the scientific value of model data of the production mode simulations will be very limited since simulations will be short due to the focus on scalability. The data is not licensed and available for research purposes.</p>
Allocation costs	No additional cost.
Data security	The data will be stored at the TGCC computing center. Data may get removed as model developments progress, see also FAIR aspect "Re-usable" above.
Ethical aspects	None.

Data reference name	Data for OASIS3-MCT performance and quality evaluation
Contact	Sophie Valcke, valcke@cerfacs.fr
Data summary and description	<p>Objectives: Evaluate the performance and interpolation quality of OASIS3-MCT with data produced with standard coupled test-cases and benchmarks.</p> <p>Relation to work programme: WP1. OASIS3-MCT is used in EC-Earth and in the IPSL model, see Tasks 1.1 and 1.2, D1.1 and D1.3.</p> <p>Data generation: Standard coupled test-cases and benchmarks are regularly used to evaluate the performance and interpolation quality of OASIS3-MCT when new developments are included in the sources.</p> <p>Data format/type: The performance numbers are usually written to text files by the test-case programs and are post-processed to draw scalability graphs. The data used to evaluate the interpolation quality are stored in NetCDF files giving the interpolation error over the target grid.</p> <p>Expected data size: Less than 1 GB.</p>
FAIR aspects	<p>Findable: CERFACS contact will always be provided when showing the results based on the data and CERFACS will provide indication on how to get the data on Zenodo to anyone requesting it.</p> <p>Accessible: If this data is requested to be publicly available in the process of submitting a paper on the performance and interpolation quality of OASIS3-MCT_5.0, then it will be made available via Zenodo.</p> <p>Interoperable: The data will be available in standard text files and NetCDF files</p> <p>Re-usable: This data will be on open access with no specific licensing during and after the end of project.</p>
Allocation costs	CERFACS will be responsible for this data and there are no estimated costs for making it FAIR.
Data security	A backup of the original data will be automatically made at CERFACS.
Ethical aspects	None.

Data reference name	Performance results of HPCW benchmarks on different computing systems
Contact	Ralf Müller, ralf.mueller@dkrz.de
Data summary and description	<p>Objectives: Store the performance results of HPCW benchmarks on different computing systems to allow reproducibility, comparisons and maintainability.</p> <p>Relation to work programme: WP3. See DoA, Task 3.4 for details.</p> <p>Data generation: Data rare produced by executing the HPCW benchmarks on a computing system.</p> <p>Data format/type: Text file(s).</p> <p>Expected data size: Not defined yet.</p>
FAIR aspects	<p>Findable: The data will be stored in an internal part of the project repository (redmine), later it will be made publicly available in a publication and linked correspondingly.</p> <p>Accessible: At first it will be accessible in the internal project repository. Later, a subset will be made publicly available in a publication.</p> <p>Interoperable: None.</p> <p>Re-usable: Yes, in particular for performance comparison. Licensing etc. has not been defined yet. Long-term archival and use is anticipated; its actual realisation (hosting, support) is subject to project work.</p>
Allocation costs	To be identified, if any.
Data security	Data is secured by the internal project repository security.
Ethical aspects	None.

Data reference name	Performance analysis data
Contact	Kim Serradell; kim.serradell@bsc.es
Data summary and description	<p>Objectives: Performance data extracted via the EXTRAE library from model runs in PARAVR format mode.</p> <p>Relation to work programme: WP1. This performance analysis data is needed to extract information from model runs to identify bottlenecks or possible improvements in WP1.</p> <p>Data generation: Data is generated via model simulations using a wrapper to intercept calls. The list of hardware counters and metrics is selected before monitoring the run (in a XML configuration file). Traces can be distributed and viewed/analysed in any computer with PARAVR software.</p> <p>Data format/type: PARAVR (PRV) trace format.</p> <p>Expected data size: O(Gigabytes).</p>
FAIR aspects	<p>Findable: Traces will be referenced in deliverables D1.1 using a DOI.</p> <p>Accessible: Traces will be uploaded to Zenodo or EUDAT and will thus be made publicly accessible.</p> <p>Interoperable: PRV traces are analysed with PARAVR viewer and distributed with a file listing the metrics gathered in the trace.</p> <p>Re-usable: Traces are re-usable.</p>
Allocation costs	No additional cost.
Data security	Data will stay on Zenodo or EUDAT servers.
Ethical aspects	None.

Data reference name	Training material
Contact	Sophie Valcke, valcke@cerfacs.fr
Data summary and description	<p>Objectives: ESIWACE2 organises trainings in different HPC areas i.e. IO, DSLs, C++, coupling, data analytics and containerisation. The material produced will be used for online or face-to-face sessions and will also be presented at two summer schools.</p> <p>Relation to work programme: WP6. See DoA, Task 6.2 for an overview.</p> <p>Data generation: The data is produced by the different partners setting up the trainings for ESIWACE2.</p> <p>Data format/type: Online digital media as Open Educational Resources (OER) material (https://www.oercommons.org) that will be available under a permissive CC-by licence and can be reused by teachers and researchers outside the consortium.</p> <p>Expected data size: Not known yet.</p>
FAIR aspects	<p>Findable: Being distributed as OER material available on https://www.oercommons.org, the data is easily findable.</p> <p>Accessible: The data will be freely available on https://www.oercommons.org under a permissive CC-by licence.</p> <p>Interoperable: Nothing is specifically needed as prerequisite to be able to use the data.</p> <p>Re-usable: It will be used in ESIWACE2 and will be easily reusable by teachers and researchers outside the consortium.</p>
Allocation costs	Every ESIWACE2 partner will take care of the material produced by the subtask the partner is responsible for (see DoA, WP 6, subtasks of Task 6.2). There is no cost expected for making it FAIR.
Data security	The material will be available on https://www.oercommons.org and a backup version will exist for each training on the ESIWACE2 partner sites.
Ethical aspects	None.

3. Glossary

WP	Work Package
BSC	Barcelona Supercomputing Center
DYAMOND	DYnamics of the Atmospheric general circulation Modeled On Non-hydrostatic Domains
HPCW	High-Performance Climate and Weather
DoA	Description of Action
OER	Open Educational Resources
IO	Input/output
DSL	Domain-specific Language
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable

4. History of changes

History of changes		
Version	Date	Change
1.0	30.06.2019	First version